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Effect of the surface etching on the cenospheres coating by silver nanoparticles

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Abstract. Cenospheres can be functionalized by an adequate metallic coating. A universal method to produce a metallic coating is the well-known polyol process. Both noble metals and most of the transition metals can be obtained by chemical reduction of the corresponding metal salts in presence of hot polyols. Hot ethylene glycol is typically used for the reduction of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) to elemental silver, $\text{Ag}(0)$. Owing to the capability of ethylene glycol to act as surface steric stabilizer, the metallic phase is obtained in form of spherical nanoparticles. Thus, when cenospheres are present during the chemical reduction of silver nitrate in presence of hot ethylene glycol, silver nanoparticles are precipitated on the cenospheres surface. Here, we have found that such precipitation is strongly influenced by the particle roughness and therefore it takes place only in the case cenospheres have been chemically etched by sodium hydroxide (NaOH) aqueous solution.

1. Introduction

Cenospheres (CFs) represent a novel type of ceramic material [1,2] characterized by unique structural/geometrical potentialities. Consequently, CFs constitute a very interesting type of substrate for functional solid phases like metal catalysts (e.g., Pt, Pd), magnetic metallic alloys, electrical/thermal conductors, antiseptic/antibacterial solid phases (e.g., Ag, Cu, Au), fluorescent/phosphorescent solids, etc [3,4]. There are many different reasons for using CFs as a substrate for depositing functional solids. For example, they have an inert chemical nature, since they are ceramic materials (precisely, silico-aluminate compounds); therefore, the CFs surface can be coated by many types of substances without to observe a chemical interaction with them. In addition, these particles are lightweight solids due to their hollow structure (they are mechanically resistant thin spherical shells). Further, CFs have a perfectly spherical shape and therefore they have the geometry characterized by the maximum value of the surface/volume ratio. Finally, CFs are perfect substrates for coatings and in the present experimental investigation they have been used as a substrate for the most common type of solid substance with

antimicrobial, antiseptics and antifungal properties, which is the nanostructured zero-valent (elemental) silver (i.e., silver particles with a size of only a few nanometer tens).

In order to develop a method for preparing a variety of lightweight functional solids in a powdered form, the CFs have been modified by using a universal technique for the synthesis of zero-valent metals in a pure and alloyed form, named 'the Polyol Process' [5,6]. The polyol process represents a well-known chemical scheme for the synthesis of noble metals (e.g., Ag, Au, Pd, Pt), transition metals (e.g., Cu, Co, Ni, Fe, etc.) and metallic alloys in a micrometric size range. In this chemical reaction a polyol (like ethylene glycol, diethylene glycol, etc.) is used as a chemical reductant of the metal precursor, precipitation medium for the metallic phase and surface sterical stabilizer to avoid particle aggregation. The metal precursor consists of a metallic salt high soluble in the liquid polyol to be used as a reductant. In order to increase the capability of polyols to reduce the metallic cations, the reduction reaction is generally performed at the polyol boiling temperature. Usually, the obtained metallic phase is made of highly monodispersed and perfectly spherical particles of micrometric size. Noble metals are very easy to obtain by this approach compared to transition metals that require high temperatures (high molecular weight polyols, like tri-ethylene glycol or tetra-ethylene glycol, must be used since the boiling point is related to the molecular weight) and much longer time periods.

In the present investigation, silver has been used as a model to verify the possibility to exploit such synthesis route for modifying the CFs surface [7,8]. Silver has relevant antimicrobial properties [9,10] and the prepared lightweight powder can be exploited for such important technological application but also for other uses, like for example, electrically or thermally conductive powdered material, plasmonic properties, etc. The novelty of the proposed approach is represented by the possibility of coating the hollow CFs structure by a continuous solid phase layer characterized by useful functional properties. Therefore, these composite core-shell particles are lightweight and capable to exhibit unique technological potentialities in industrial fields like magnetic materials, EMI shielding, chemical or biological sensors (e.g., detecting gases, toxins or bacteria).

2. Experimental

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , 99,9%, Aldrich) has been used as a metallic silver precursor salt since it is the only silver salt moderately soluble in alcohols (both organic and inorganic silver salts are completely insoluble solids). Since silver is a noble-metal, the AgNO_3 precursor can be easily reduced by diols and therefore ethylene glycol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}_2$, EG, Aldrich, 99.0%) has been selected as reductant. Both reactants have been used in the as received form. In addition, EG has not been used at its boiling point (197.3°C) but at lower temperatures (i.e., 80°C and 100°C) since chemical reduction of a noble-metal can be easily achieved. In particular, 250 mg of CFs were dispersed in the EG liquid phase (100ml) under magnetic stirring and the system was heated at the selected reaction temperature (80°C or 100°C), then the silver nitrate solution in the EG (0.6 mol/l) was rapidly added by a syringe, under stirring. The reaction was allowed to complete in 2h. The starting liquid CFs dispersion rapidly turned to a yellow coloration due to the formation of silver clusters, and then it became brown-black with the progress of the chemical reduction and growth of the metallic phase. At reaction end, the product was isolated by ultra-filtration (PTFE filter, $0.22\mu\text{m}$, Jinlong), repeatedly washed by water and ethanol, recovered from the filter and then dried in oven at 100°C for 4h.

It has been experimentally found that the coating process can follow two different pathways: (i) the homogeneous nucleation of the silver phase, where nuclei are generated in the liquid phase,

and (ii) the heterogeneous nucleation of the silver phase, where the nuclei are generated on the surface of the CFs. In this study it has been found that the coating process can be effective (heterogeneous nucleation) only in the case the ceramic surface has been chemically etched. In particular, in order to allow a uniform and continuous surface coating by silver, a chemical pre-treatment of the ceramic surface must be performed. Such pre-treatment consisted in the etching of the ceramic surface by using a desilication reaction (silicate conversion to silicic acid), that can be performed by strong alkaline species. In particular, a sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 99.3%, ACS reagent) aqueous solution (0.5 mol/l) has been used. CFs were etched at 50°C for 120 minutes, under slow magnetic stirring. Stirring is required to maintain CFs uniformly dispersed in the NaOH solution during the pre-treatment. It must be pointed out that according to a microscopical investigation of the morphology of treated CFs (see Figure 1), the stirring process did not significantly break the spherical shape of the CFs. According to the literature [11], the surface activation by sodium hydroxide is used both to clean the CFs surface and to activate them.

Figure 1. Optical micrograph of etched CFs (NaOH 0.5mol/l, 50°C, 120min) (20X, transmitted natural light)

Optical images were obtained by an Optical Microscopy (OM) (Olympus, mod. BX 51 M), equipped by a halogen lamp power supply unit (Olympus, mod. TH4-200). The morphological characterization was performed by using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Quanta 200 FEG microscope, FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA). X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) experiments were carried out with a Malvern PANalytical diffractometer (Malvern, UK) equipped with a nickel filter and Cu $K\alpha$ radiation in order to identify and define the crystalline phases. The average crystal size (τ) was evaluated through the Scherrer formula:

$$\tau = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$$

where τ is the average size of the crystallite domains, $K=0.94$ is a dimensionless shape factor, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the broadening at half the maximum intensity (FWHM), θ is the Bragg angle.

3. Results and Discussion

The precipitation of elemental silver on the CFs surface was conveniently investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Indeed, the presence of an electrical conductor (the metallic phase) on a dielectric substrate (the ceramic phase) was easily detected because of the very strong contrast, which characterized such type of biphasic systems. A large amount of secondary electrons (SE) can be emitted from the electrically conductive phase, while the insulator phase

appeared dark for the low amount of emitted SE due to charging phenomena. When CFs were used in the as received form, the presence of silver nanoparticles on the ceramic surface was not observed in the SEM micrographs, independently from the adopted polyol process conditions (i.e., reduction temperature and silver nitrate concentration). As an example, Figure 2 shows the as received CFs sample exposed to the precipitation of silver nanoparticles at 80°C for 150min. As clearly visible in this SEM picture, the CFs surface resulted completely free from the presence of an electrically conductive metallic (silver) phase and therefore, during the polyol process, the reduced metal should be homogeneously nucleated in the liquid system.

Figure 2. SEM micrograph of as received CFs exposed to the precipitation of Ag-NP produced by polyol process (80°C, 150min).

According to the SEM analysis of the CFs surface (see Figure 3a), the texture of the ceramic phase was constituted of acicular crystals of comparable size, embedded in a continuous amorphous phase. After the chemical etching treatment, such texture changed significantly (see Figure 3b). Indeed, the crystalline phase resulted better visible and slightly coming out of the embedding phase, therefore the surface roughness of this ceramic phase resulted significantly increased.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of as received CFs (a) and etched CFs (b) at the same magnification.

As clearly visible in Figure 4, metallic silver was precipitated on the surface of etched CFs and the nanoscopic metallic crystals appeared prevalently at the edges of the acicular alumino-silicate crystals coming out of the ceramic substrate. In other words, when silver was precipitated in presence of etched CFs, the metallic phase separation took place according to a heterogeneous nucleation mechanism (differently, a homogeneous nucleation mechanism was involved in the silver precipitation in presence of an unetched CFs sample).

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of etched CFs coated with Ag-NP produced by PP (80°C, 150min) and etched CFs coated with Ag-NP produced by PP (100°C, 150min) (F).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed the morphological observations performed by SEM investigation (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. XRD diffractograms of as received CFs (black line), etched CFs (red line), as received CFs exposed to the precipitation of Ag-NPs produced by PP (80°C, 150min) (blue line), etched CFs coated with Ag-NPs produced by PP (80°C, 150min) (green line) and etched CFs coated with Ag-NPs produced by PP (100°C, 150min) (pink line).

In fact, the XRD diffractograms of the modified CFs, in addition to CFs diffraction pattern, included the most intensive peaks belonging to the elemental silver [11]. Therefore, such analysis confirmed the concomitant presence of elemental silver and alumino-silicate phases in the products of the PP obtained after CFs etching. In addition, this XRD analysis showed that silver crystals have a nanoscopic size because the diffraction peaks appeared significantly broadened and characterized by a low signal-to-noise ratio. The average size of silver nanocrystals was evaluated by the Sherrer equation applied to the most intensive peak in the silver diffraction pattern (i.e., $2\theta = 38^\circ$) and an average size of (21 ± 2) nm was found for the sample of CFs coated by Ag-NPs produced by polyol process performed at 80°C for 150min, and (28 ± 2) nm for the sample of CFs coated by Ag-NPs produced by polyol process performed at 100°C for 150min.

4. Conclusions

CFs can be functionalized by silver nanoparticles prepared by using the PP approach. If their surface has been sufficiently etched by a hot alkaline aqueous solution, Ag-NP nucleates on the CFs surface. Morphological characterization made by SEM shows as Ag-NP are present exclusively on the crystalline part of the CFs texture. XRD confirm the presence of Ag on the CFs' surface and XRD evidence their nanoscopic size.

Data Availability

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16627453>

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